

EFFECT OF MANUFACTURE AND LAMINATE DESIGN ON ENERGY ABSORPTION OF OPEN CARBON- FIBRE/EPOXY SECTIONS

A. Jackson^{a*}, S. Dutton^a, A. J. Gunnion^b and D. Kelly^a

^a School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South
Wales, 2052, Australia

^b Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures, 506 Lorimer Street,
Fishermans Bend, 3207, Victoria, Australia

*a.jackson@crc-accs.com.au

SUMMARY

The effects of manufacturing techniques and laminate design on the crush performance of carbon-fibre/epoxy DLR crush elements were experimentally investigated. Specific energy absorption did not vary with manufacturing technique and was found to be the highest with a quasi-isotropic lay-up. Interleaving with thermoplastic films improved steady state crushing force.

Keywords: Energy absorption, Mechanical testing, Crushing, Tooling, Interleaving

INTRODUCTION

Since the 1970's there has been considerable interest in the crashworthiness of composite materials, driven mainly by the increasing use of these materials in automobiles and aircraft. It is desirable from a crashworthiness perspective for designated areas of structures to fail in a progressive manner, thereby reducing the maximum acceleration on occupants and eliminating injuries and fatalities in relatively mild impacts and minimising them in all severe but survivable mishaps [1].

Failure by progressive crushing differs from catastrophic failure modes in that a stable region of failure exists over which the crushing load is approximately constant. Progressive failure of composites is usually achieved by applying a compressive load to a suitably-triggered component. Triggering usually involves a geometric gradient feature in the component which causes locally high stress relative to the rest of the part. The high local stress initiates microfracture in the triggered region [2], which progresses through the gradient feature, and eventually forms a stable crush zone.

Much work has been performed on the static and dynamic axial crushing of open and closed sections made from composite materials, e.g. [3-20]. These studies have focused on the effect of matrix and fibre properties, geometry, loading rates and triggering mechanisms. Farley [4] described three main progressive failure modes: (1) transverse shearing, (2) lamina bending and (3) local buckling. These first two failure modes have become more commonly referred to as fragmentation and splaying modes respectively [2, 10, 16, 21] and are typically observed only in brittle fibre-reinforced materials.

Of current interest is the effect that laminate design, including ply lay-up and toughening through thermoplastic interleaving, has on the Specific Energy Absorption (SEA) of crush elements designed by the Deutsches Zentrum für Luft-und Raumfahrt (DLR; German Aerospace Centre). DLR crush elements are omega shaped sections and were developed as a standard specimen configuration to characterise the crush performance of materials. DLR crush elements were chosen over other section designs as they are easy to fabricate and provide reproducible crush failures under dynamic and static loads [22]. Specimens with varying ply orientation were manufactured and tested quasi-statically. There is known to be a trade off between including load carrying plies parallel to the crush direction (0°) versus $\pm 45^\circ$ or 90° plies to provide hoop reinforcement in the crushing of carbon fibre/epoxy sections [3, 16, 23, 24]. Achieving the optimal balance depends on the material properties, and thus it is hard to predict the optimal lay-up for new materials. Once the optimal lay-up was determined, specimens were then manufactured with different thin thermoplastic films as interleaves between plies in an attempt to toughen the laminate and increase SEA during crushing.

Crush tests were also carried out in order to determine the effect that manufacturing techniques of the open omega sections have on crush performance. Male, female and closed tool moulds were used to manufacture specimens using both autoclave curing and Out-of-Autoclave Curing (OAC). Some previous studies have looked at the effect of processing conditions on the material properties and the resulting crush performance [9, 25, 26], however these have investigated tubes manufactured using resin transfer moulding or wet lay-up, not pre-preg techniques.

The work presented in this paper is being carried out as part of a project to develop a crashworthiness design capability for Australian industry by the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS).

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Materials

DLR crush elements were manufactured using three carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy pre-pregs as listed in Table 1. Both the Hexcel M18/1 and MTM44 fabrics are designed primarily for autoclave curing and can also be used for OAC.

Table 1: Carbon-fibre epoxy pre-pregs used in manufacture of crush specimens

Designation	Manufacturer	Architecture	Areal weight (g/m^2)	Nominal Fibre V_f	Nominal CPT (mm)
M18/1/43%/G939	Hexcel	4HS	220	0.55	0.227
MTM44-1FR-468	ACG	4HS	220	0.55	0.227
MTM44-1FR-756	ACG	Uni weave (10% transverse fibres)	160	0.55	0.165

The two thermoplastic films used as interleaves were 0.003” Pyralux[®] LF0111 and 0.002” Pyralux[®] LF0110. Pyralux[®] films are 0.001” DuPont Kapton[®] Polyimide (PI) film coated with a B-staged modified acrylic on one and both sides respectively for LF0110 and LF0111.

Specimen Manufacture

Manufacturing Methods Comparison

DLR crush element lengths were laid up by hand using HexPly M18/1 4HS pre-preg onto male, female and closed tools and envelope bagged for autoclave or oven (vacuum only) curing. Table 2 lists the lengths manufactured; with there being at least three specimens in each batch. The autoclave and oven (vacuum only) cure cycles are shown in Figure 2. Note that for the oven cured specimens actual ramp-up rates were approximately 1°C/min. Lengths were then trimmed to the DLR crush element geometry shown in Figure 1, and a 45° chamfer was machined into one end of each specimen using custom-built tooling. Specimens were then either potted in Araldite Kit K 106 resin or fixed in an aluminium clamp (see Figure 3) for testing.

Figure 1: DLR crush element geometry (dimensions in mm)

Table 2: DLR crush element specimens for the manufacturing methods comparison

Batch ID	Cure	Tooling	Lay-up
CR-M18-MC-01	Autoclave	Male	[0, 90, 0, 90, 0, 90, 0]
CR-M18-MC-02	Autoclave	Female	
CR-M18-MC-03	Autoclave	Closed	
CR-M18-MC-04	Autoclave	Male	
CR-M18-MC-05	Autoclave	Male	
CR-M18-MC-06	Autoclave	Female	[0, 90, 0, 90, 0, 90, 0, 90, 0]
CR-M18-MC-07	Oven	Male	
CR-M18-MC-08	Oven	Female	
CR-M18-MC-09	Autoclave	Male	

Figure 2: M18/1 cure cycle; (L) autoclave, (R) oven (vacuum only)

Figure 3: Crush specimen support configurations: (L) potted, and (R) clamped

Lay-up Comparison

DLR crush element lengths were laid up by hand using M18/1, MTM44-1FR-468 and MTM44-1FR-756 into female moulds with the lay-ups shown in Table 3. Specimens were autoclave cured in the case of the M18/1, whilst MTM44-1FR specimens were oven (vacuum only) cured. Three DLR crush elements from each batch were tested.

Table 3: DLR crush element specimens for the lay-up comparison

Batch ID	Material	Lay-up
CR-M18-LC-01	M18/1	$[(0, 90)_2, 0, (90, 0)_2]$
CR-M18-LC-02	M18/1	$[0, 90, +45, 0, 90, 0, +45, 90, 0]$
CR-M18-LC-03	M18/1	$[0, +45, 90, -45, 0, -45, 90, +45, 0]$
CR-M18-LC-04	M18/1	$[+45, -45, 0, 90, 0, 90, 0, -45, +45]$
CR-M18-LC-05	M18/1	$[+45, -45, 0, +45, -45, +45, 0, -45, +45]$
CR-M18-LC-06	M18/1	$[(+45, -45)_2, +45, (-45, +45)_2]$
CR-MTM468-LC-07	MTM44-1FR-468	$[0, 90]_{2s}$
CR-MTM468-LC-08	MTM44-1FR-468	$[0, +45, 90, -45]_s$
CR-MTM468-LC-09	MTM44-1FR-468	$[+45, -45]_{2s}$
CR-MTM756-LC-10	MTM44-1FR-756	$[0, 90]_{3s}$
CR-MTM756-LC-11	MTM44-1FR-756	$[+45, -45]_{3s}$
CR-MTMHYB-LC-12	MTM44-1FR-468 / -756	$[0, +45, 0, -45, 0]_s$ Highlighted plies are -756 fabric

Interleaving Trials

M18/1 pre-preg was laid up by hand into female moulds and autoclave cured. Interleaving of the thermoplastic films was made every ply or every second ply (as shown in Table 4) with three DLR crush elements in each batch.

Table 4: DLR crush element specimens for the interleaving trials

Batch ID	Material / Lay-up	Thermoplastic
CR-M18-LF0111-I	M18/1 $[0, +45, 90, -45]_s$	LF0111, interleave every ply
CR-M18-LF0111-II		LF0111, interleave every 2 nd ply
CR-M18-LF0110-I		LF0110, interleave every ply
CR-M18-LF0110-II		LF0110, interleave every 2 nd ply

Test Method

Testing was performed in an INSTRON 1185 100kN machine with a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min for the first 20 mm of vertical displacement at which point the rate was increased to 20 mm/min for the final 30 mm of vertical displacement. Load and crosshead displacement were recorded at 10 Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Manufacturing Methods Comparison

Stable, progressive crushing was initiated and sustained for all specimens. The load typically ramped up linearly over the first 2 – 2.5 mm of vertical displacement (corresponding with the chamfer height) to a maximum value in the region of 23 – 28 kN, after which the crushing load stabilised until the end of the test.

Typical fragmentation behaviour of crush specimens is shown in Figure 4. The crush specimens failed in the ‘splaying’ crush failure mode, with internal and external fronds forming which were progressively bent and deformed as the platens came together. Some frond fragments broke off completely from the crushed specimen, and smaller pieces of debris (major dimension typically < 3 mm) were also produced. A small debris wedge was present where the main central wall crack had been propagating. Energy absorption in the failure mode observed is primarily through crack growth (longitudinal and interlaminar), friction between separated lamina layers and between the specimen and the loading surface and bending / fracture of fibres in the fronds [4].

Figure 4: Crushed M18/1 specimens: (L) front view, (R) top view

Total energy absorption was calculated by integrating the test data for the entire test period (0 to ~50 mm displacement). This was then divided by the weight of the crushed portion of the specimen to give the SEA for each test. The weight of the crushed portion of specimen was calculated by multiplying the total crush distance by the mass per length of each specimen which was determined from pre-test measurements. Steady State Crush Force (SSCF) was calculated as the mean load for the test period from 3

mm vertical displacement to the end of the test. Steady State Crush Stress (SSCS) for a given test is calculated as the SSCF divided by the measured pre-test cross-sectional area, and is a useful means for comparing specimens with different numbers of plies.

Table 5 lists the peak load, SSCF, SSCS and SEA for all manufacture tooling and test fixture permutations tested. As can be seen, there is very little variation in SEA between any of the tooling configurations. A minimum of three specimens were tested for each permutation, and SSCF was highly repeatable within each data set.

There was a slightly higher range of SEA values observed for the cure cycle comparison testing, as shown in Table 6, with male-tooled specimens performing the poorest on average. Note however that the oven-cured male-tooled specimens generally had poorer compaction and low resin content in the small radius area.

Table 5: Manufacturing tooling comparison results

Manufacture Tooling	Test Fixture	Peak Load (kN) [std dev]	SSCF (kN) [std dev]	SSCS (MPa) [std dev]	SEA (kJ/kg) [std dev]
Male	Potted	24.7 [1.45]	20.1 [0.25]	140 [0.11]	83.1 [0.51]
Male	Clamped	25.7 [0.74]	20.0 [0.45]	139 [3.53]	82.2 [1.68]
Female	Potted	24.7 [.046]	19.4 [0.38]	118 [0.64]	79.8 [0.50]
Female	Clamped	24.9 [1.27]	19.6 [.036]	118 [0.83]	79.7 [0.18]
Closed	Potted	23.5 [0.92]	18.0 [.059]	127 [0.14]	82.4 [0.82]
Closed	Clamped	22.6 [0.66]	17.7 [0.17]	124 [1.19]	79.9 [0.84]

Table 6: Cure cycle comparison results

Manufacture Tooling	Manufacture Method	Peak Load (kN) [std dev]	SSCF (kN) [std dev]	SSCS (MPa) [std dev]	SEA (kJ/kg) [std dev]
Male	Autoclave	25.0 [0.31]	21.9 [0.076]	132 [1.3]	79.7 [0.83]
Female	Autoclave ¹	28.0 [1.02]	25.0 [0.61]	130 [2.7]	87.2 [2.97]
Female	Autoclave ²	26.6 [1.61]	22.2 [0.11]	123 [.62]	81.4 [0.80]
Male	Oven	25.1 [1.04]	22.7 [0.43]	126 [2.9]	79.1 [2.00]
Female	Oven	27.9 [0.45]	24.6 [0.46]	127 [2.9]	83.1 [2.64]

¹ $V_f = 50.5\%$, ² $V_f = 54.8\%$

Overall the spread in SEA values is relatively small, and appears to be correlated more to variations in fibre volume fraction (V_f) of specimens rather than manufacturing method. Figure 5 shows the SSCS and SEA with respect to V_f for each batch of specimens manufactured, and it appears that SEA is highest around a V_f of around 51%. The slight downward trend in SEA with increasing V_f is consistent with a study by Farley [3] on the axial crushing of carbon fibre – epoxy sections. Jacob et al. [27] also found a similar trend for random short carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, however this depended upon the fibre length. As V_f increases, the overall density of the laminate will also increase since fibre density is greater than resin density. Hence if the specific energy is to increase with increasing V_f then the SSCS must increase by an amount that exceeds the increase in material density [2, 10]. Thus it should be noted that an increase in V_f causing an increase in SSCS may not always necessarily improve the SEA capability.

Figure 5: Variation of SSCS and SEA with V_f

Lay-up Comparison

Crush test results for the specimens with varying ply lay-up are shown in Table 7 and Figure 6. For the M18/1 specimens, the variation in SEA from the orthogonal 0/90 to ± 45 lay-up was relatively small. Maximum SEA was obtained from the quasi-isotropic configuration (CR-M18-LC03), although interestingly when the ± 45 plies were biased towards the outside of the specimen with the same overall content of 0/90 and ± 45 plies (CR-M18-LC04), the SEA was lower. All the M18/1 specimens failed in a very similar mode to that already described. Although, with increasing ± 45 ply content, it was found that less axial splits (and therefore fronds) were formed, the crushed portion of the specimen was less cohesive, and the SSCF showed greater instability.

MTM44-1FR specimens exhibited larger variations between the two extremes of 0/90 and ± 45 lay-ups. MTM44-1FR-468 (4HS) specimens had higher SEA than M18/1 for 0/90 and quasi-isotropic lay-ups, but lower for the ± 45 arrangement. The fragmentation behaviour of MTM44-1FR-468 was similar to that of M18/1, although the ± 45 lay-ups (CR-MTM468-LC09) had quite large fractured pieces in addition to the usual smaller debris (see Figure 7) which caused higher crush force instability and lower SEA. The quasi-isotropic $[0/+45/90/-45]_S$ 4HS specimens showed the highest SEA (104 kJ/kg), displaying the same trend observed in the M18/1 specimens shown in Figure 6.

MTM44-1FR-756 specimens showed different fragmentation behaviour and lower SEA compared to the 4HS fabrics. Whilst they still failed in the ‘splaying’ mode the $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens disintegrated more (Figure 8), with the splayed fronds springing back up after the test, indicating that less fibre fracture had occurred. MTM44-1FR-756 $[+45/-45]_{3S}$ specimens failed in sections along the 45° axis, resulting in large pieces of the specimen breaking off and not being crushed (Figure 9). The crushing force therefore varied significantly during each test, and the SEA was relatively low.

The hybrid MTM44-1FR-468 / 756 specimens were tested in an attempt to harness the greater load carrying capability of 0° oriented UNI-weave plies combined with the stability and reinforcement of 4HS plies. These specimens resulted in the highest SEA of all specimen sets (114 kJ/kg), failing in splaying mode in a manner combining the different fragmentation behaviours already described. The main wall crack occurred down the midplane of the specimen, leaving 0° UNI-weave plies exposed, which sprang

back up slightly after the load was removed (Figure 10). The underlying crushed portion of the specimen was less cohesive and similar to that of the ± 45 4HS specimens.

Table 7: Lay-up comparison results

Batch ID	Peak Load (kN) [std dev]	SSCF (kN) [std dev]	SSCS (MPa) [std dev]	SEA (kJ/kg) [std dev]
CR-M18-LC-01	28.0 [1.02]	25.0 [0.61]	130 [2.7]	87.2 [3.0]
CR-M18-LC-02	32.3 [0.13]	28.0 [0.66]	137 [3.6]	88.3 [3.5]
CR-M18-LC-03	33.8 [1.37]	28.5 [1.27]	140 [6.7]	90.6 [5.0]
CR-M18-LC-04	31.0 [0.52]	26.6 [0.67]	126 [2.4]	86.5 [1.6]
CR-M18-LC-05	32.2 [4.40]	27.8 [1.92]	129 [8.3]	89.6 [5.8]
CR-M18-LC-06	29.1 [0.97]	24.0 [0.48]	113 [1.6]	79.4 [3.6]
CR-MTM468-LC-07	30.6 [0.57]	27.2 [0.46]	150 [2.3]	100.8 [0.79]
CR-MTM468-LC-08	31.6 [1.28]	27.8 [1.24]	165 [6.8]	104.3 [3.3]
CR-MTM468-LC-09	25.2 [0.56]	17.5 [0.55]	96 [2.4]	71.2 [2.5]
CR-MTM756-LC-10	29.1 [0.70]	23.6 [0.39]	115 [3.3]	77.9 [0.46]
CR-MTM756-LC-11	25.7 [0.86]	16.3 [2.30]	83 [13.5]	57.4 [10.7]
CR-MTMHYB-LC-12	41.1 [0.91]	34.4 [0.93]	184 [4.2]	114.3 [3.9]

Figure 6: Variation in SEA with relative $\pm 45^\circ$ ply content

Figure 7: Crushed MTM44-1FR-468 specimen: (L) $[0/90]_{2s}$, (R): $[+45/-45]_{2s}$

Figure 8: Crushed MTM44-1FR-756 $[0/90]_{3s}$ specimen: (L) front view, (R) top view

Figure 9: Crushed MTM44-1FR-756 $[+45/-45]_{3s}$ specimen: (L) front view, (R) top view

Figure 10: Crushed hybrid MTM44 specimen: (L) front view, (R) top view

Thermoplastic Interleaving

The results of the crush testing of M18/1 specimens interleaved with thin thermoplastic films are shown in Table 8, including the closest non-interleaved specimen from the previous testing as a baseline. Note however that the baseline specimens (CR-M18-LC-03) had one extra 0/90 ply at the midplane compared to the interleaved specimens, due to the fact that the thickness had to be kept close to 2 mm to fit the chamfering and test tooling, and the thermoplastic interleaves added too much thickness to use the same 9-ply lay-up.

Addition of the thermoplastic films in between every ply increased the SSCF. Fragmentation behaviour was typical of that already described for the non-interleaved M18/1 specimens, and residual thermoplastic was visible on the fractured surfaces (see Figure 11). However, the increase in SSCF was not large enough to offset the increase in specimen density due to the addition of the thermoplastic film, and the SEA was approximately equivalent to the baseline specimens.

Interleaving of brittle, fibre reinforced composites with thermoplastic layers has been shown to increase Mode I, Mode II fracture toughness as well as Inter-Lamina Shear Strength (ILSS) [28-33] and increasing these properties has been shown to increase SEA in crushing of composite materials [13, 34-37]. The small improvements in SSCF in this work indicate that this toughening can increase energy absorption through increasing the energies associated with crack propagation. Current estimates [38-40] put the energy associated with crack propagation during crushing of composite sections at between 5% and 20%, so unless a toughening strategy improves crack propagation energies by a substantial amount there will be no significant increase in total energy absorption. In the current case, a small improvement in total energy absorption was found with interleaving every ply with PI film; however the increase did not translate to an improvement in SEA due to the increase in density.

Table 8: Interleaving trials results

Batch ID	Peak Load (kN) [std dev]	SSCF (kN) [std dev]	SSCS (MPa) [std dev]	SEA (kJ/kg) [std dev]
Baseline (CR-M18-LC-03 no interleaves)*	33.8 [1.37]	28.5 [1.27]	140 [6.7]	90.6 [5.0]
CR-M18-LF0111-I	37.1 [1.54]	31.3 [0.92]	138 [3.8]	92.0 [2.9]
CR-M18-LF0111-II	31.5 [0.86]	26.3 [0.82]	131 [1.4]	89.4 [0.95]
CR-M18-LF0110-I	35.8 [0.74]	29.1 [0.47]	134 [2.4]	90.9 [2.6]
CR-M18-LF0110-II	30.6 [0.81]	25.5 [0.38]	129 [1.9]	89.3 [1.0]

* one extra 0/90 ply at midplane compared to interleaved specimens

Figure 11: Crushed interleaved specimen (CR-M18-LF0111)

CONCLUSION

Manufacture and quasi-static crush testing of DLR crush elements have been performed to investigate the effect that laminate design and manufacturing method have on crush performance. Steady state crushing was initiated in all specimens tested via a machined chamfer at the top edge of the specimen.

Male and female open tooling and closed mould tooling configurations were used to manufacture DLR crush elements, and two test specimen support types were used; clamped and potted. Energy absorption performance was found to be not influenced by any of the tooling configurations tested. Similarly, there was no correlation between curing method (autoclave versus OAC) and crush performance. The variation observed in SEA is due to variation in V_f .

The response to changes in lay-up arrangement depended upon the material used. M18/1 showed little variation in SEA with lay-up, however MTM44-1FR-468 had higher SEA for orthogonal 0/90 and quasi-isotropic lay-ups, but lower SEA for the ± 45 lay-up. MTM44-1FR-756 unidirectional material did not perform as well as the 4HS fabrics, however, a hybrid MTM44-1FR-468 and -756 lay-up produced the highest SEA (114 kJ/kg) of all the configurations tested.

Thermoplastic interleaving every ply with Pyralux[®] PI film increased the SSCF, however this increase was not large enough to offset the increase in specimen density from adding the thermoplastic material, and SEA was found to remain the same as for non-interleaved specimens.

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References

1. Zimmermann RE, Merritt NA. Aircraft Crash Survival Design Guide, Vol. 1. *USAAVSCOM TR 89-D-22A* 1989, Fort Eustis: Simula Inc.
2. Ramakrishna S. Microstructural design of composite materials for crashworthy structural applications. *Materials & Design* 1997;18(3):167-173.
3. Farley GL, Jones RM. Energy absorption capability of composite tubes and beams. *NASA Technical Memorandum 101634* 1989, Hampton: U.S. Army Aviation Research and Technology Activity - AVSCOM.
4. Farley GL, Jones RM. Crushing Characteristics of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Composite Tubes. *J Compos Mater* 1992;26(1):36-50.
5. Hamada H, Ramakrishna S. Scaling effects in the energy absorption of carbon-fiber/PEEK composite tubes. *Compos Sci Technol* 1995;55(3):211-221.
6. Hamada H, Ramakrishna S, Sato H. Effect of fiber orientation on the energy absorption capability of carbon fiber/PEEK composite tubes. *J Compos Mater* 1996;30(8):947-63.
7. Mahdi E, Hamouda AMS, Mokhtar AS, Majid DL. Many aspects to improve damage tolerance of collapsible composite energy absorber devices. *Compos Struct* 2005;67(2):175-187.
8. Mamalis AG, Manolakos DE, Ioannidis MB, Papapostolou DP. On the response of thin-walled CFRP composite tubular components subjected to static and dynamic axial compressive loading: experimental. *Compos Struct* 2005;69(4):407-420.
9. Melo JDD, Silva ALS, Villena JEN. The effect of processing conditions on the energy absorption capability of composite tubes. *Compos Struct* 2008;82(4):622-628.
10. Ramakrishna S, Hull D. Energy absorption capability of epoxy composite tubes with knitted carbon fibre fabric reinforcement. *Compos Sci Technol* 1993;49(4):349-356.
11. Sigalas I, Kumosa M, Hull D. Trigger mechanisms in energy-absorbing glass cloth/epoxy tubes. *Compos Sci Technol* 1991;40(3):265-287.
12. Solaimurugan S, Velmurugan R. Influence of fibre orientation and stacking sequence on petalling of glass/polyester composite cylindrical shells under axial compression. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 2007;44(21):6999-7020.
13. Solaimurugan S, Velmurugan R. Progressive crushing of stitched glass/polyester composite cylindrical shells. *Compos Sci Technol* 2007;67(3-4):422-437.
14. Song H-W, Du X-W, Zhao G-F. Energy absorption behavior of double-chamfer triggered glass/epoxy circular tubes. *J Compos Mater* 2002;36(18):2183-2198.
15. Tao WH, Robertson RE, Thornton PH. Effects of material properties and crush conditions on the crush energy absorption of fiber composite rods. *Compos Sci Technol* 1993;47(4):405-418.
16. Hull D. A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre-reinforced composite tubes. *Compos Sci Technol* 1991;40(4):377-421.
17. Thornton PH. Energy Absorption in Composite Structures. *J Compos Mater* 1979;13(3):247-262.
18. Thornton PH. The crush behavior of glass fiber reinforced plastic sections. *Compos Sci Technol* 1986;27(3):199-223.
19. Thuis HGSJ, Metz VH. Influence of trigger configurations and laminate lay-up on the failure mode of composite crush cylinders. *Compos Struct* 1993;25(1-4):37-43.
20. Mamalis AG, Robinson M, Manolakos DE, Demosthenous GA, Ioannidis MB, Carruthers J. Crashworthy capability of composite material structures. *Compos Struct* 1997;37(2):109-134.
21. Ramakrishna S, Hamada H. Energy absorption characteristics of crash worthy structural composite materials. *Key Eng Mater* 1998;141-143(Pt 2):585-620.

22. Kindervater CM, Johnson AF, Kohlgrüber D, Lützenburger M, Pentecote N. Crash and impact simulation of aircraft structures - hybrid and FE based approaches. In: *European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering*. Barcelona, Spain: ECCOMAS, 2000.
23. Bolukbasi AO, Laananen DH. Energy absorption in composite stiffeners. *Composites* 1995;26(4):291-301.
24. Fleming DC, Nicot F. Crushing of flat graphite/epoxy laminates using a column specimen. *J Compos Mater* 2003;37(24):2225-2239.
25. Turner TA, Warrior NA, Robitaille F, Rudd CD. The influence of processing variables on the energy absorption of composite tubes. *Compos Part A* 2005;36(9):1291-1299.
26. Warrior NA, Turner TA, Robitaille F, Rudd CD. Effect of resin properties and processing parameters on crash energy absorbing composite structures made by RTM. *Compos Part A* 2003;34(6):543-550.
27. Jacob GC, Starbuck JM, Fellers JF, Simunovic S. Effect of fiber volume fraction, fiber length and fiber tow size on the energy absorption of chopped carbon fiber-polymer composites. *Polym Compos* 2005;26(3):293-305.
28. Aksoy A, Carlsson LA. Interlaminar shear fracture of interleaved graphite/epoxy composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 1992;43(1):55-69.
29. Chen SF, Jang BZ. Fracture behaviour of interleaved fiber-resin composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 1991;41(1):77-97.
30. Gao F, Jiao G, Lu Z, Ning R. Mode II delamination and damage resistance of carbon/epoxy composite laminates interleaved with thermoplastic particles. *J Compos Mater* 2007;41(1):111-123.
31. Li L, Lee-Sullivan P, Liew KM. The influence of thermoplastic film interleaving on the interlaminar shear strength and mode I fracture of laminated composites. *J Eng Mater Technol* 1996;118(3):302-309.
32. Warrior NA, Turner TA, Robitaille F, Rudd CD. The effect of interlaminar toughening strategies on the energy absorption of composite tubes. *Compos Part A* 2004;35(4):431-437.
33. Sela N, Ishai O. Interlaminar fracture toughness and toughening of laminated composite materials: a review. *Composites* 1989;20(5):423--435.
34. Yuan Q, Kerth S, Karger-Kocsis J, Friedrich K. Crash and energy absorption behaviour of interleaved carbon-fibre-reinforced epoxy tubes. *J Mater Sci Letters* 1997;16(22):1793-1796.
35. Cauchi Savona S, Hogg PJ. Effect of fracture toughness properties on the crushing of flat composite plates. *Compos Sci Technol* 2006;66(13):2317-2328.
36. Daniel L, Hogg PJ, Curtis PT. The relative effects of through-thickness properties and fibre orientation on energy absorption by continuous fibre composites. *Compos Part B* 1999;30(3):257-266.
37. Hadavinia H, Ghasemnejad H. Effects of mode-I and mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness on the energy absorption of CFRP twill/weave composite box sections. *Compos Struct* 2009;89(2):303-314.
38. Ghasemnejad H, Blackman BRK, Hadavinia H, Sudall B. Experimental studies on fracture characterisation and energy absorption of GFRP composite box structures. *Compos Struct* 2009;88(2):253-261.
39. Mamalis AG, Manolakos DE, Demosthenous GA, Ioannidis MB. Energy absorption capability of fibreglass composite square frusta subjected to static and dynamic axial collapse. *Thin-Walled Structures* 1996;25(4):269-295.
40. Mamalis AG, Manolakos DE, Demosthenous GA, Ioannidis MB. The static and dynamic axial crumbling of thin-walled fibreglass composite square tubes. *Compos Part B* 1997;28(4):439-451.